

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD
FOR TACROLIMUS IN BULK AND MARKETED GEL**

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Abstract:

Aim: The proposed research work aims to develop and validate the UV spectrophotometric method for Tacrolimus in bulk and marketed Gel (Tacvido forte) as per ICH guidelines. **Method:** The UV spectrophotometric method has been developed and validated to estimate the Tacrolimus in bulk and marketed formulation. The λ_{max} for Tacrolimus in methanol was observed at 250nm and 295nm. **Result:** Tacrolimus was found in the linear range in the concentration of 0.05-0.09 mg/ml at 250nm and 0.1-0.3 mg/ml at 295nm and the regression coefficient was found to be 0.999 for both at 250nm and 295nm. The limit of detection and the limit of quantification at 250nm was

found to be 1.93 and 5.83. The limit of detection and limit of quantification at 295nm was found to be 1.94 and 5.87 respectively. **Conclusion:** The UV spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Tacrolimus in bulk and marketed Gel has been successfully developed and validated.

Keywords: Tacrolimus, UV spectrophotometry, Methanol, Gel, validation.

1. Introduction:

Tacrolimus (FK506) is a calcineurin inhibitor and immunosuppressant. It has the chemical formula $C_{44}H_{69}NO_{12}$ and is a 23-membered macrolide lactone. (Figure 1) that was discovered for the first time in 1987 in *Streptomyces tsukubaensis*. The US Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) originally approved it for liver transplantation in 1994 [1].

Figure.1: Chemical structure of Tacrolimus (TAC)

Tacrolimus is regarded as a gold standard immunosuppressive medication [2]. Tacrolimus's immunosuppressive properties are a result of immunophilin's affinity to attach to it. Immunophilin is a broad family of cytosolic proteins [3] that is divided into subgroups based on how they interact with immunosuppressants. FK506 binding proteins (FKBPs) engage with Tacrolimus or rapamycin, whereas cyclophilins interact with cyclosporine A. After associating with their respective immunosuppressant, the immunophilins create a binary complex that inhibits T-cell activation and proliferation [4]. Tacrolimus is also used topically for the treatment of T-cell mediated illnesses such as eczema and psoriasis, as well as for the management of dry eye in dogs and cats [5]. Tacrolimus, at high doses and for long periods, can cause nephrotoxicity, neurotoxicity, infections, hypertension, posttransplant diabetes, and cancers. [6]. Tacrolimus is practically insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in hexane, and soluble in chloroform, acetone, ethanol, methanol, diethyl ether, ethyl acetate [7-9]. The main aim of our proposed research work is to develop and validate the UV spectrophotometric method for estimation of Tacrolimus in bulk and marketed Gel (Tacvido forte) formulation.

2. Materials and methods:

Tacrolimus was obtained as a gift sample from Biocon pharmaceuticals, methanol (HPLC grade) was purchased from research labs, tacvido Gel was purchased from a local market pharmacy shop, and other chemicals were of analytical grade.

2.1.Preparation of standard stock solution:

The stock solution was prepared by accurately weighing 10mg of Tacrolimus transferred in a 10ml volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol, and volume was made up to the mark by the same solvent.

2.2.Preparation of working standard solution:

Pipette out 0.5ml and 1.0ml of standard stock solution in two different 10ml volumetric flask and add 3ml of methanol, mixed well and make up the volume up to the mark by methanol (concentration 50 μ g/ml, and 100 μ g/ml). The selection of analytical wavelength was done by scanning the working standard solution in UV spectrophotometer in the range of 200-400nm.

2.3.Validation of method:

The developed method was validated using the brand name "tacvido forte" Gel nominally containing 0.1% of Tacrolimus, according to the label, by determining the following parameters: linearity, precision, accuracy, the limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantitation (LOQ), following the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH Q2(R1) guidelines (ICH, 2005).

2.4.Linearity:

Linearity was determined by constructing analytical curve, with five calibration points for Tacrolimus with the concentrations 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09 mg/ml and 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3 mg/ml. The absorbance values were plotted against respective concentrations of Tacrolimus to obtain the analytical curves. The results were subjected to regression analysis by the least square method to calculate the calibration equation and correlation coefficient.

2.5.Calibration curve

The aliquots of the working standard stock solution were diluted with methanol to obtain the concentration range of 0.05-0.09 mg/ml and 0.1-0.3 mg/ml for Tacrolimus. The calibration plot was generated by replicate analysis (n = 3) of all the concentrations by

measuring the absorbance at 250nm and 295nm. Statistical parameters related to calibration curve like slope, intercept, co-efficient of correlation, standard deviation, and relative standard deviation were determined.

2.6.Accuracy:

Accuracy was determined by spiking a blank sample with the analyte at three different concentrations (80%, 100%, and 120%). The standard deviation of results was calculated and accuracy was determined in terms of % recovery.

2.7.Precision:

The precision of the method was determined by intra-day and inter-day precision. The intermediate precision of the method was assessed by carrying out the analysis on three different days (inter-days). Intraday precision was measured between three-time intervals and interday precision was measured between three consecutive days. Three determinations for three concentrations covering the selected range were carried out. Precision was evaluated in terms of mean % R.S.D. Percentage relative standard deviation was calculated.

2.8.Limit of detection and limit of quantification:

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were calculated by taking the replicate determination of blank. The calculation was done according to the equations. $LOD = 3.3 \times s/m$, $LOQ = 10 \times s/m$. Where "s" is the standard deviation of the absorbance of the sample and "m" is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

2.9.Sample preparation:

To prepare the sample solution, 1ml of Gel equivalent to 10mg Tacrolimus was transferred to a 10ml volumetric flask and volume made up with methanol to obtain the concentration of 1000 μ g/ml. The solution was filtered and 0.5ml and 1ml of the filtrate were taken in two different 10ml volumetric flask and dilution was done using methanol up to mark to obtain a concentration of 0.05mg/ml and 0.1mg/ml.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The absorption spectrum shows the highest peak for Tacrolimus at 250nm and 295nm that was selected for analytical studies as shown in figure.2.

Figure.2: Spectrum showing λ_{max} at 250nm and 295nm.

Analytical data

The optical features and statistical measures for the proposed technique are described in Table 1 under optimized experimental situations. An examination of the calibration graph's intercept, slope, correlation coefficient, and linearity reveals that it has acceptable linearity. The proposed method's sensitivity is indicated by the detection limit and slope. 15 independent determinations at three concentration levels were used to conduct precision studies on the proposed strategy. Table 1 shows the relative standard deviations that were determined. A typical addition approach was used to confirm the accuracy of the suggested method by adding a known quantity of pure medication to the dosage form. Table 2 summarizes the findings, which are found to be satisfactory.

Table-1: Validation Parameters

S.No.	Parameters	Results	Results
1.	Absorption Wavelength (nm)	250nm	295nm
2.	Linearity range (mg/ml)	0.05-0.09	0.1-0.3
3.	Standard regression equation	$Y=1.49x+0.076$	$Y= 0.732x-0.005$
4.	Slope	1.49	0.732
5.	Intercept	0.076	0.005
6.	Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.999	0.999
7.	Accuracy (% recovery \pm SD)	99.15 \pm 0.87	99.75 \pm 0.43
8.	Precision (% RSD)	0.8 (Intra-day)	0.4 (Intra-day)
		0.9 (Inter-day)	0.5 (Inter-day)
9.	LOD (mg/ml)	1.93	1.94
10.	LOQ (mg/ml)	5.83	5.87

Figure.3:- Calibration curve of Tacrolimus in methanol at 250nm

Figure.4:- Calibration curve of Tacrolimus in methanol at 295nm

Table - 2: Determination of accuracy by percentage recovery method at 250nm

Ingredient	Quantity of formulation (Gel) (mg/ml)	Level of addition (%)	Quantity added (mg/ml)	Drug found (mg/ml)	%Recovery	Average % recovery
Tacrolimus	0.050	0	0	0.051	102	-
	0.050	80	0.040	0.092	102.22	99.15±0.87
	0.050	100	0.050	0.098	98	
	0.050	120	0.060	0.107	97.27	

Table - 3: Determination of accuracy by percentage recovery method at 295nm

Ingredient	Quantity of formulation (Gel) (mg/ml)	Level of addition (%)	Quantity added (mg/ml)	Drug found (mg/ml)	%Recovery	Average % recovery
Tacrolimus	0.10	0	0	0.11	110	-
	0.10	80	0.08	0.183	101.67	99.75±0.43
	0.10	100	0.10	0.197	98.50	
	0.10	120	0.12	0.218	99.09	

4. Conclusion:

The method was developed successfully within concentration range of 0.05 – 0.09mg/ml at 250nm and 0.1-0.3mg/ml at 295nm. The correlation coefficient value was found to be 0.999 for both 250nm and 295nm and the method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The validated method is found to be applicable for the determination of Tacrolimus in Gel dosage form.

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